

Impact of Online Games on Youth -A Study With Reference To Coastal Karnataka

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Abstract

In this modern era Technology plays an important role in every walk of human life. The rise in the use of the internet has led to many changes in our daily life. People are using the latest technologies for information and entertainment which are providing wide ranges of benefits to human community. For infotainment people are depending on social media and online gaming in advanced model. In this virtual world online gaming touches its highest level.

Today's youth are using technology in a variety of ways, from texting and tweeting to chatting, online gaming, and posting through a variety of Internet portals. It can often seem like youth are using technology and the internet for a large part of the day. Understanding youngsters and technology can seem a little overwhelming. It sometimes seems like young people's lives revolve around their phones and technology. From the internet and social media, to phones, apps, games, television and other types of technology, technology is increasingly becoming an essential part of our lives. Many young people – often referred to as 'digital natives' – haven't known it any other way. Gaming is a powerful and immersive medium that attracts children, young people and adults of all ages.

This study focuses on the various opinion and impacts of online games on youth. The collection of primary data for the present study is from different places of coastal Karnataka (which includes the Districts such as Dakshina Kannada, Udupi and Uttara Kannada using a structured questionnaire, in addition to the secondary data. The study will show whether playing online games has impact on their study as well as on the physical and mental health

Key words: Coastal Karnataka, Youths, Technology, Online Games, Mental Health.

Introduction

In this modern era Technology plays an important role in every human life. The rise in the use of the internet has led to many changes in our daily life. People are using the latest technologies for information and entertainment which are providing wide ranges of benefits to human community. For infotainment people are depending on social media and online gaming in advanced model. In this virtual world online gaming touches its highest level.

Today's youth are using technology in a variety of ways, from texting and tweeting to chatting, online gaming, and posting through a variety of Internet portals. It can often seem like youth are using technology and the internet for a large part of the day. Understanding youngsters and technology can seem a little overwhelming. It sometimes seems like young people's lives revolve around their phones and technology. From the internet and social media, to phones, apps, games, television and other types of technology, technology is increasingly becoming an essential part of our lives. Many young people – often referred to as 'digital natives' – haven't known it any other way. Gaming is a powerful and immersive medium that

attracts children, young people and adults of all ages.

Objectives Of The Study:

The objective of the study are as follows:

1. To analyze the impact of online gaming on physical, psychological and social wellbeing of young people.
2. Evaluate the potential benefits and drawbacks of online games.
3. Investigate the reasons why some players prefer online games over traditional games and vice versa

Research Design and Methodology

The study has been conducted using primary data as well as secondary data. Secondary data was collected from different published sources. Primary data was collected by using structured survey. 100 respondents were randomly selected from Dakshina Kannada, Udupi and Uttara Kannada districts of Karnataka state. Spot observations and discussions were also used. Data has been represented in tabular form.

Limitations of The Study:

1. The sample size is limited to selected places of Coastal Karnataka only
2. It indicates the number of people to be surveyed, though large number of sample give

more reliable results than small samples but due to time constraint the data was restricted to 100 respondents.

The data has been collected regarding the gender wise classification of the respondents. The respondents have been classified into male and female. The collected data have been provided both through the table 1.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Gender Wise Classification of The Respondents

Table .1 Gender Wise Classification Of The Respondents

Gender	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
TOTAL	100	100

Source: Survey data N=100

Analysis and Interpretation

The above table 1 shows the gender wise classification of respondents. Out of 100 respondents, 60 respondents are male accounting for 60% and remaining 40 respondents are female accounting for 40%. Based on the above analysis it

has been interpreted that majority of the respondents i.e.60% are male.

2. Age Wise Classification of The Respondents

The data has been collected regarding the age wise classification of the respondents. The respondents have been classified into 11 to 15 years, 16 to 18 years, 19 to 21 years, and 22 to 26 years old. The collected data has been provided both through the table 2.

Table 2. Age Wise Classification Of The Respondents

Age	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
11-15	8	8
16-18	12	12
19-21	21	21
22-26	59	59
Total	100	100

Source: Survey data N=100

Analysis and Interpretation

Above Table.2 shows the distribution of the respondents according to age. 59 percentage of the respondents fall in the age group 22-26 years, 21 percentage of the respondents fall in the age group

19-21 years, 12 percentage of the respondents fall in the age group of 16-18 years, and remaining 8 percentage of respondents are fall in the age group of 11-15 years. Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority (59%) of the respondents fall in the age group of 22-26 years old.

Table 3 Educational Qualification Of The Respondents

Qualification	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
School	10	10
PUC	11	11
Graduation	32	32
Post-Graduation	40	40
Other	7	7
TOTAL	100	100

Source: Survey data N=100

Analysis And Interpretation

Above Table 3 shows the distribution of the respondents according to the Education. Out of 100 respondents 40% of the respondents are post-graduates, 32% of the respondents are graduates, 11% respondents are PUC passed, 10% of the respondents are school going children, and the remaining 7% of the respondents are learnt other

courses. Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority (40%) of the respondents are Post-Graduates.

4. Occupation Wise Classification Of The Respondents

The data has been collected regarding the occupation wise classification of the respondents. The respondents have been classified into Students, Employees, Professionals, Business persons, Not

employed, and other. The collected data has been provided both through the table 4.

Table 4 Occupation Wise Classification Of The Respondents

OCCUPATION	NO. OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
Student	63	63
Employee	30	30
Professionals	1	1
Business	1	1
Not Employed	5	5
Other	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

Source: Survey data N=100
Analysis and Interpretation

Above Table 4 shows the distribution of the respondents according to the Occupation. Out of 100 respondents 63% of the respondents are Students, 30% of the respondents are employees, 5% of the respondents are Not employed, 1% of respondent is Professional and 1% is Business

person. Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority (63%) of the respondents are Students.

5.Effect Of Online Games On Physical Health

The data has been collected from the respondents regarding effect of online games on physical health of the player. The collected data has been provided both through the table 5.

Table 5. Effect Of Online Games On Physical Health

Effects	No.Of Responses	Percentage
Tiredness	20	10.86
Less sleep	24	13.04
Eye strain	48	26.08
Headache	35	19.02
Neck pain	22	11.95
Not affected	35	19.02
Others	0	0
TOTAL		100

Source: Survey data N=100
M.R.R= 1.84

Note: 1. Responses are not equal to 100 because of multiple responses.

2. Multiple Response Rate is equal to total number of responses divided by the number of respondents.

Analysis And Interpretation

Above Table 5.shows the opinion of the respondents regarding the effect of online games on their physical health. Out of 100 respondents for 26.08% of respondents online gaming have caused eye strain, 19.02% of respondents have experienced

headache, 19.02% of respondents are not affected by any physical health problem, for 13.04% of respondents it has caused less sleep, 11.95% have experienced neck pain, and for 10.86% of respondents online gaming has caused tiredness. Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority (26.08%) of respondents have experienced eyestrain after playing online games.

6. Effect Of Online Games On Mental Health

The data has been collected from the respondents regarding effect of online games on mental health of the player. The collected data has been provided both through the table 6.

Table 6. Effect Of Online Games On Mental Health

EFFECTS	NO.OF RESPONSES	PERCENTAGE
Causes aggression	12	9.23
Leads to anxiety	15	11.53
Stress	25	19.23
Not affected	49	37.69
Not sure	29	22.30

Other	0	0
TOTAL		100

Source: Survey data **M.R.R=1.3**
N=100

Note: 1. Responses are not equal to 100 because of multiple responses.

2. Multiple Response Rate is equal to total number of responses divided by the number of respondents.

Analysis And Interpretation

Above Table 6.shows the opinion of the respondents regarding the effect of online games on their mental health. Out of 100 respondents 37.69% of respondents says that online gaming have not affected their mental health, 22.30% of respondents are not sure whether online gaming have impacted

on their mental health or not, for 19.23% of respondents it has caused stress, 11.53% have experienced anxiety, and for 9.23% of respondents online gaming has caused aggression. Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority (37.69%) of respondents are not affected by online games mentally.

7. Online Gaming Helps In Quick Thinking, Fast Analysis and And Problem Solving Skills

The data has been collected to know the opinion of the respondents if online gaming helps them in quick thinking, fast analysis and improves problem solving skills. The collected data has been provided both through the table 7.

Table 7 Online Gaming Helps In Quick Thinking, Fast Analysis And And Problem Solving Skills

Responses	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	64	64
No	36	36
TOTAL	100	100

Source: Survey data **N=100**

Analysis And Interpretation

Above Table 7.shows the opinion of the respondents regarding whether online gaming helps them in quick thinking fast analysis and problem solving skills. Out of 100 respondents 64 people answered yes accounting for 64%, 36 people answered no accounting for 36%. Based on the above analysis it

has been interpreted that majority (64%) of respondents says online gaming helped them in quick thinking fast analysis and problem solving.

8.Advantages Of Online Games Over Traditional Games

The data has been collected to know the opinion of the respondents about the advantages of online games over traditional games. The collected data has been provided both through the table 8.

Table 8. Advantages Of Online Games Over Traditional Games

Advantages	No. Of Responses	Percentage
Convenience & accessibility	44	20.09
Wide variety of game options	58	26.48
Multiplayer & online community features	37	16.89
Realistic graphics & immersive experience	35	15.98
Ability to play with friends remotely	45	20.54

Source: Survey data **M.R.R=2.19**
N=100

Note: 1. Responses are is not equal to 100 because of multiple responses.

2. Multiple Response Rate is equal to total number of responses divided by the number of respondents.

Analysis And Interpretation

Above Table 8.shows the opinion of the respondents regarding the advantages of online games over traditional games. Out of 100 respondents 26.48% of respondents says that online games gives wide variety of game options, 20.54%

of respondents says that it gives the ability to play with friends remotely, 20.09% of respondents says that it is convenient and easy to access, 16.89% of respondents says that it provides multiplayer and online community features, and remaining 15.98% of respondents says that it has realistic graphics and provides immersive experience. Based on the above analysis it has been interpreted that majority (26.48%) of respondents says that online games have wide variety of game options compared to traditional games.

Findings

Based on the analysis and interpretation some of the major findings have been listed below:

1. From the study it is found that majority of the respondents are male (60%)
2. From the study it is found that majority (59%) of the respondents fall in the age group of 22-26 years old.
3. The study depicts that most of the respondents were post graduates i.e, 40%
4. From the study it is found that majority (63%) of the respondents are students
5. The study reveals that majority (26.08%) of respondents have experienced eyestrain after playing online games.
6. From the study it was found that majority (26.48%) of respondents thinks that online games have wide variety of game options than traditional games.

Suggestions

1. Online gaming has both positive and negative impacts on children, youth and adults so one must use it appropriately and make use of technology in a wise way.
2. For those players who have had a negative impact on their eyesight they should reduce the number of hours they play online games.
3. For those gamers whose sleeping pattern is affected negatively, should try to maintain balance between their gaming hours and sleeping hours.
4. Try to maintain balance between studies or work and playing video games. This can help students to improve grades or helps in doing their work better.
5. All online gaming platforms must have maximum time limit of playing per day to protect the uncontrollable human mind from addiction.
6. Even though there are less number of people faced impact on their mental health, it can be advised that violent games can be played as less as possible because it can impact the mind of the gamer sometimes.

CONCLUSION:

Online gaming has emerged as a popular and successful source of entertainment and played by people of all ages especially by youth. Its main aim is to entertain people and also indirectly to make them addictive to improve gaming industry. The Study reveals that there is positive online gaming effect on youth of Mangalore. Boys spend more time playing online games compared to girls. Through this study we analyzed that playing online games have caused negative effects to youth to the certain extent. Generation z are not likely to be addictive towards online games. On the positive side online games help in enhancing mental development, critical and quick thinking, improving

various skills, making fast analysis and in stress relief also. Real life skills like coordination and team management also get improved by playing online games like PUBG because it requires in game communication.

They prefer both traditional and online games equally. Online games have wide varieties of game options, and more convenient compared to traditional games but still people prefer both because both the games are best in their own way. Online games are just the substitutes for traditional games not the replacement. As an outcome of the study it can be concluded that the online gaming has its positive and negative impacts in the real world. Online games can be a boon or curse to the gamer depending upon the game he plays and the number of hours the gamer spends on playing video games. In short , online games can help the youth in their real life skills if they can learn to play it wisely and if not it can cause problems for the player in the future.

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